

Empathic Architecture for Safe Spaces: An Ethnographic Approach to Trauma-Informed Design

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Abstract

La ricerca analizza l'importanza di progettare spazi sicuri che tengano conto delle esigenze specifiche delle persone sopravvissute ad abusi in età infantile. In continuità con i presupposti dell'*inclusive design*, vengono presentate le principali intersezioni fra trauma e spazialità, con la finalità di informare i professionisti e le professioniste dell'ambiente costruito delle conseguenze sullo spazio dovute all'esposizione prolungata ai traumi. Integrando interviste qualitative ed etnografia visiva, lo studio propone l'applicazione di alcuni principi per una progettazione architettonica consapevole sugli effetti dei traumi psicologici, in particolare nella creazione di edifici residenziali.

The research highlights the importance of understanding how spaces can be designed to accommodate the needs of survivors of child sexual abuse and promote inclusive design. By exploring the intersections of trauma and spatial design, the study seeks to inform practitioners of the built environment in creating residential architecture, prioritising a holistic approach to safety and accessibility. Incorporating qualitative interviews and visual ethnography, this study explores how trauma-informed design principles can be implemented into collaborative practices to re-envision place-making through a lens of trauma awareness: sensory modulation zones, layered spaces, and self-connection points

Parole chiave

Abusi sessuali infantili, Inclusive Design; Significato dei luoghi; Spazi sicuri; Trauma-Informed Design

Child sexual abuse; Inclusive Design; Place Meaning; Safe Spaces; Trauma-Informed Design

Introduction

The perception and representation of spaces hold profound significance for survivors of child sexual abuse (CSA)¹, influencing their sense of safety and belonging (WILLIS et al., 2015). Within architectural discourse, understanding these impacts is essential to developing trauma-informed design practices that prioritise the needs of survivors². This study explores how childhood trauma shapes spatial experience, aiming to contribute to bridging a critical architectural research gap (ALLCOCK, 2019). The research examines how trauma affects spatial perception and seeks to suggest architectural practices gathered throughout multiple participant observation sessions. Findings argue that an anthropological approach to trauma-informed design, through qualitative interviews and visual ethnography, can encourage architects and practitioners to create functional, empathetic, and inclusive spaces for those affected by childhood trauma.

Methodology

The method used was designed to thoroughly examine how trauma³, space, and design are interconnected. The fieldwork took place over a year and included monthly online interviews and on-site observations with 30 participants aged 18 to 55 (two male, twenty-three female, and five non-binary). All the individuals are survivors of childhood abuse, and half of them have been diagnosed with a form of disability. Eight of them are members of ethnic minorities or have experienced a migration background. Except for two Italian participants living abroad, all the rest are based in Italy. Subjects were recruited through two calls for participants disseminated in different ways: one among adult members of Meti Onlus (an association representing survivors of child abuse) and another through the author of the research's social media.

In-depth qualitative interviews provided rich, firsthand accounts of how childhood trauma impacts spatial perception and the concept of home. This method was chosen for its capacity to capture complex, subjective experiences that quantitative data might overlook. Following the guidelines for ensuring safety (ALESSI & KAHN, 2022), written informed consent was obtained, and interviews were conducted individually in Italian, so the quotes in this study were translated.

Complementing the interviews, visual ethnography was employed to observe participants' interactions with their spaces over the course of a year. This method allowed for documenting their environments, capturing changes in spatial arrangements and design elements contributing to their sense of safety and agency. An integral part of this methodology was the use of "verbal maps", a behavioural experiment to collect sketch maps and verbal descriptions from participants. They were asked to externalise their spatial mental representations of their homes, combining graphic and word descriptions. No specific cartographic expertise was requisite, and no evidence of accuracy was sought. These representations detailed areas associated with safety or danger and explained the reasons behind these associations, providing insights into how survivors structure their spaces. This activity has also been repeated after furniture and room layout changes or following a relocation.

Intersections of Trauma and Architecture

The theoretical framework of trauma and space reveals how distressing and disturbing experiences impact perceptions of spaces and the concept of home (WILLIS et al., 2016). Everyone undergoes trauma in their lives at some point or another. Many people quickly recover, while for others, the persistent hauntings of the initial crisis become deeply ingrained in their lives, leading to conditions such as post-traumatic stress disorder (PTSD) and lasting adverse effects on health. The likelihood of long-term traumatic stress depends on various factors, such as the intensity and duration of a crisis, an individual's physical resilience, support systems, and preexisting

psychological conditions (CLEMENS et al., 2018). Whatever the case, experiences of trauma can distort the sense of safety and belonging, transforming familiar environments into sources of distress. Survivors often reinterpret spatial elements, associating them with their trauma and fundamentally altering their relationship with their surroundings (TUCKER, 2010).

Research indicates that trauma significantly affects how individuals perceive and navigate their environments (ADAMS-HUTCHESON, 2017). Notable Judith Herman's work (2001) highlights that trauma disrupts an individual's connection to space, influencing their need for safety and control. This is echoed in findings that emphasise the importance of safety and trust within spatial contexts, as these are fundamental to trauma recovery (AREL, 2018). Existing literature on trauma-informed design emphasises the need for spaces that are sensitive to these experiences (SCHROEDER et al., 2021). Studies show that environments designed with trauma-informed principles can promote healing (OWEN & CRANE, 2022): this involves physical safety and creating spaces that evoke comfort and empowerment. For instance, architectural designs that incorporate clear sightlines, access to nature, soothing colour palettes, opportunities for personalisation, and flexible spaces can transform spaces into therapeutic environments that aid recovery (BAFNA & CHAMBERS, 2015). Architects and practitioners can help reconstruct a survivor's sense of home by creating inclusive and supportive environments, turning spaces into havens of comfort and security.

Designing is not just about programming, space planning and project feasibility. It is also about creating the right atmosphere, effect, and ambience (ASFOUR, 2019). The goal is to make architecture a medium for processing human sensations and experiences (PATRIA et al., 2018). A significant body of research and discussion has urged the architectural profession to move away from a purely technical and visually-focused approach (YAZICI, 2013). The theories and concepts of "atmosphere" (ZUMTHOR, 2006), "affective space" (DE MATTEIS, 2020) and "ambience" (PALLASMAA, 2019) centre around emphasising the emotional and sensory aspects of space, materials, and shapes (ROONEY et al., 2017). By changing how we approach design and construction, trauma-informed architecture emerges as a pivotal tool for addressing mental health from an anthropological perspective and as a living entity that forms a physical, cultural and sensory connection with the people using it. In individuals who have experienced trauma, their bodies may perceive and signal "danger" before their conscious mind has even registered the thought (SHERIN & NEMEROFF, 2011). As a result, the body promptly initiates a range of physiological stress responses, including the instinct to fight, flee, freeze, or exhibit fawning behaviour (WALKER, 2003). This cascade of responses occurs rapidly and instinctively, often without conscious awareness, shaping the individual's immediate reactions to perceived threats (ZINGELA et al., 2022). An ethnographic approach to trauma-informed design can leverage architecture and how trauma affects the space bodily.

Environmental Triggers in the Residential Architecture

For survivors of childhood abuse, the concept of home often becomes complex and paradoxical (MONNAT & CHANDLER, 2015). This is even more evident in the light of the increased likelihood that individuals who survived intra-family abuse⁴ were exposed to harm and threats in or close to the same place they lived (LOINAZ et al., 2019). Rather than a refuge, home may serve as a reminder of trauma, complicating the sense of safety typically associated with domestic spaces. This fractured sanctuary challenges survivors to navigate environments that can evoke past experiences of fear and vulnerability (HERMAN, 2001).

During ethnographic observations that led to this study, participants described the home as a site of both potential healing and re-traumatisation. For example, they used specific language to carve out what they consider safe spaces: see terms

like «my sanctuary», «safe haven», and «my bubble», which are vivid indicators of the emotional and psychological protection these areas provide. Conversely, the language used to describe triggering or dangerous spaces is equally telling: see words like «suffocating», «dark», or «claustrophobic», which reveal the negative emotions tied to these areas. This issue also includes re-experiencing traumatic stress due to current situations that mirror past traumatic memories, such as entering the place where the abuse occurred or encountering patterns, furnishings (fig. 1) and designs that recall that haunted place (ROSATO & CAMPO, 2025). See the use of roundabout phrases like “non-home”, reflecting the need for nuanced language to describe the opposite of “home” as a haven. Without sensitivity to trauma’s impact, buildings may unwittingly perpetuate trauma by triggering individuals through common environmental elements. Unpleasant scents like body odour, mildew, and smoke can evoke traumatic memories, so proper ventilation systems and odour-neutralising materials are crucial for well-being and stress reduction. This presents an opportunity for architecture to heighten or calm the body’s response to perceived stressors by modulating environmental stimuli and atmospheres.

Trauma-Informed Design Principles

Practical experience has shown that incorporating a trauma-informed design (TID) into building design can enhance the decision-making process and ultimately improve outcomes for residents without adding to the cost or complexity of construction (HARTE, 2019). In the context at hand, TID emphasises creating safe and inclusive residential architecture that addresses the needs of childhood abuse survivors. Understanding the influence of spatial organisations is a prerequisite for designing and managing spaces that prevent the conditions underlying abuse from arising; in fact, building design can influence the behaviours and performance of people using those spaces (DE PAIVA, 2018).

Addressing trauma through design may initially seem niche, but it serves a large, frequently silenced population (BRIERE & ELLIOTT, 2003). Many survivors experience persistent feelings of shame that impact various aspects of their lives (MACGINLEY et al., 2019). Additionally, for those with visible or invisible disabilities, the effects of childhood trauma can be exacerbated (ANDRADE & REDONDO, 2022), making

1/ Verbal map sketch from a participant depicting the word ‘divano’ (couch). The repetitive and swirling lettering reflects the participant’s compulsive focus on couches, who is reluctant to sit on couches due to past trauma. This visualisation illustrates the participant’s emotional turbulence and the complexity of their sensory and psychological responses to this piece of furniture.

trauma-informed design essential for creating supportive environments that cater to diverse needs. The experience of trauma is deeply connected to the physical body and its reaction to space even before it is consciously understood. Therefore, the architectural and structural elements of a building play a significant role in how trauma is experienced (STOPPANI, 2016). While each person's experience of trauma is unique, research has identified common responses and stimuli in the home (CURRY, 2017). Through visual ethnography and qualitative interviews, recurring patterns in how participants respond to trauma have been observed. Given the existing experience (GRABOWSKA et al., 2021), further observations contribute to framing three principles that accommodate CSA survivors' peculiar experiences: sensory modulation zones, layered spaces, and self-connection points. These criteria outline spatial responses to complex needs and are rooted in understanding how trauma affects the body through space.

Sensory Modulation Zones

For individuals who have experienced trauma, heightened sensory sensitivity is often a challenge (FARLEY & KEANEY, 1997). Sensory modulation zones should be designed to manage stimuli that can trigger fight, flight, freeze, or fawn responses. They recommend modulation and filtration rather than mere subtraction or addition of sensory information. On-site observation and regular interviews have shown how these stress responses can find relief through adjustable environmental patterns. Providing outlets for physical activity can offer a safe release for those in "fight" mode, allowing them to channel their energy positively. For individuals who tend to go into "flight" mode, the environment should include secluded areas where they can find solace and comfort to alleviate their fear. On the other hand, incorporating elements of excitement and stimulation can help individuals in "freeze" mode reconnect with their physical being. Lastly, those who tend to enter "fawn" mode can benefit from clearly defined physical boundaries and warm social interactions.

Some concrete applications observed employ textured walls and floors to boost visual appeal and engage multiple senses by absorbing sound, providing tactile experiences, and stimulating visual interest. This approach allows smells, sounds, sights, and kinetic potential to vary in intensity and quality. Including rocking chairs or swings introduces rhythmic motion, calming the nervous system, alleviating anxiety and promoting relaxation (HOUSTON, 1993). Using membranes like interior windows, perforated screens, or partial walls maintains openness while modulating sensory experiences, fostering connectivity without overwhelming the senses. Lastly, keyless locking mechanisms for doors, such as digital locks or simple latches, ensure individuals can secure their spaces independently. This is particularly significant because many survivors may have experienced situations where access to keys was controlled or denied by parents or caregivers.

Layered Spaces

As survivors heal, their requirements change and layered spaces accommodate their evolving needs, offering flexibility and allowing individuals to choose varying levels of social, physical, and sensory engagement over time. These spaces foster the discovery of grey zones between extremes, like compression and expansion, and personal and professional environments, which are more commonly coexisting post-pandemic. Offering a gradient provides kinetic options, allowing areas to serve multiple purposes without limiting them. This versatility maximises limited space while maintaining privacy and personal comfort within a shared environment. Breaking large spaces into smaller, manageable sections with design elements like dropped ceilings or area rugs creates a welcoming atmosphere, making them feel more intimate. Modulating spaces are also apt to be adjusted according to the

season: for example, in the summertime, the intense heat and sweating are not only uncomfortable, but the odour can also elicit traumatic memories of abuse. Private and shared bathroom spaces, designed with attention to sensory triggers and adequate soundproofing, help maintain privacy. For survivors who find mirrors triggering, using adjustable or concealable mirrors allows individuals to choose when and how to engage with their reflection.

Niches and nooks, such as alcoves or window seats, offer quiet spaces for rest and reflection while maintaining a connection to the larger environment. Survivors often find comfort in small retreats that resemble places they used to hide during abuse, such as wardrobes. Establishing the space to pitch a tent temporarily (or anything resembling it) can provide implied shelter, contributing to a balanced sense of privacy and community. Lastly, biophilic elements, such as natural materials like wood and fibres, improve acoustics and provide a calming effect through sounds like flowing water. Resorting to nature also seems motivated as it recalls 'untouched' things and, therefore, uncorrupted by anyone.

Self-Connection Points

Establishing a sense of self is a pivotal component in the restorative process for trauma survivors (QUAS et al., 2003). Self-connection points can foster a more profound sense of belonging and help to counteract feelings of isolation (ESCALERA-REYES, 2020). These points are particularly vital for those who have experienced marginalisation. For instance, environments that respect personal boundaries are essential for disabled individuals, as the presence of caregivers or family members in all aspects of life can evoke feelings of scrutiny and reduce personal autonomy. It is incredibly even more hurting if a caregiver is a perpetrator of abuse.

A suggested approach involves creating a constellation of touchpoints that cater to various identities. This allows individuals to see reflections of themselves and their experiences within the space. Accommodating rooms for personalisation is paramount for those prohibited from doing so at the time of abuse. Features like tapestries and murals are not only merely decorative but serve to extend the view of the domestic space and can also cover parts of the room that evoke trauma. In addition, ensuring the authenticity of materials and avoiding faux finishes or artificial plants conveys honesty and continuity, reinforcing trust and stability within the environment. Dedicated areas for activities like journaling, smoking, praying, meditating, exercising, creating art or self-pleasure can support emotional and spiritual needs, allowing individuals to engage in personal rituals that bring comfort and peace. Furthermore, designing spaces catering to different genders' diverse needs ensures all users' safety, connection, and confidence. Lastly, cultural resonance spaces reflect and celebrate diverse cultural identities, fostering inclusivity and respect for varied backgrounds.

Discussion and Future Directions

By integrating qualitative insights with visual documentation, the study – grounded in cultural anthropology – focuses on the interplay between trauma and space. In particular, trauma-informed design emphasises its role in creating safe and inclusive residential architecture that addresses the needs of childhood abuse survivors. The mixed-methods framework implemented for this research detected a range of actionable insights that merge into the following concepts: sensory modulation zones, layered spaces, and self-connection points. These principles are meant to recontextualise design decisions rather than serve as checklists. The provided renderings (figg. 2-7) are not proposals for furnishings but practical illustrations of such concepts.

One key concept involves the creation of 'sensory modulation zones', which aim to

2/ A conceptual rendering illustrating the creation of safe and adaptable spaces through defined physical boundaries and the modulation of spatial compression and expansion. This design approach allows for varied uses, including temporarily establishing a tent-like structure and fostering a balanced sense of privacy. The design caters to multiple identities and personal connections within the environment by incorporating a constellation of touchpoints.

3/ The use of textured walls enhances visual appeal and engages multiple senses. They are strategically employed to absorb sound and provide tactile stimulation, contributing to a calming environment. Additionally, the bed is partially integrated into the walls, offering a sense of protection. This integration serves as a refuge and includes soft sensory elements that aid individuals in freeze mode, helping them reconnect with their physical presence in the space.

4/ Dividing large spaces into smaller, more manageable sections. Use elements like dropped ceilings and area rugs to create a welcoming atmosphere. Incorporating biophilic elements such as natural wood and fibres enhances the space, improving acoustics and calming. Using authentic materials and avoiding faux finishes or artificial plants conveys a sense of honesty and continuity, contributing to a more grounded and soothing environment.

5/ Personal environments should include secluded areas where residents can find solace. Niches and nooks are integrated to offer quiet spaces for rest and reflection while maintaining a connection to the larger environment. The design also incorporates dedicated areas for personal activities or simply seeking moments of solitude, emphasising spaces catering to a wide range of emotional and individual needs.

6/ The use of membranes like perforated screens can maintain a sense of openness while modulating sensory experiences. These elements serve as outlets for physical activity, offering a safe and controlled release. The inclusion of adjustable or concealable mirrors empowers individuals by giving them the choice of when and how to engage with their reflection, thus creating a more adaptable and personally supportive environment.

7/ Implementing keyless locking mechanisms for doors can ensure that individuals can secure their spaces independently, offering a sense of autonomy and control over their environments. This approach is incredibly empowering for those who have experienced situations where access to personal spaces was restricted or controlled by others.

provide spaces that can help regulate sensory experiences and support individuals in managing their responses to stimuli. Another essential principle is the integration of 'layered spaces', which can offer varying levels of privacy and control, allowing individuals to adapt their environment to their specific needs. Additionally, the concept of 'self-connection points' emphasises the importance of creating spaces that support traumatised people in connecting with themselves and their surroundings, fostering a sense of agency and self-validation. Empathy is explored as an emotional catalyst in architecture (PALLASMAA et al., 2015), emphasising its importance in promoting an emotional connection between users and spaces (DE BOTTON, 2006). Empowering survivors by giving them control over their environment is a key aspect of recovery. This can inform design choices that prioritise autonomy and personal agency. When interpreting the study results, it is important to consider limitations. Childhood maltreatment was assessed retrospectively and through self-reported measures, which can introduce bias. Although all participants could recall detailed memories of the CSA event, distortions may have impacted data collection (LOFTUS et al., 1996). Additionally, the study had a small sample size. Further prospective studies are needed to confirm the extent to which the application of the TID principles is reasonable among the survivors and their housemates. These findings pave the way for future research on comparative studies across different cultural contexts, which can help integrate trauma-informed design principles into mainstream practice and training programs.

Notes

1. The definition of CSA chosen for this study is based on the DSM-V-TR, encompassing «any sexual act involving a child that is intended to provide sexual gratification to a parent, caregiver, or other individual who has responsibility for the child» (AMERICAN PSYCHIATRIC ASSOCIATION, 2022: 824).
2. This paper aims to convey a sense of optimism by refraining from using the term "victim" and opting for the term "survivor" when suitable.
3. In this text, "trauma" refers to experiences that cause intense physical and psychological stress reactions.
4. Intra-familial child sexual abuse is generally recognised as including abuse by a relative, such as a parent, sibling, or grandparent, as well as abuse by individuals closely linked to or considered to be part of the family, such as a foster carer or a parent's partner (GEKOSKI et al., 2016).

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